

TECHNOLOGY AND THE GLOBAL GOAL ON ADAPTATION

TECHNICAL BRIEF

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The Paris Agreement explicitly links climate change adaptation and mitigation with means of implementation (MoI). Particularly for adaptation, Article 7.13 states that “continuous and enhanced international support shall be provided to developing country Parties” in accordance with all MoI-related Articles of the Paris Agreement (9, 10, and 11).

Article 7 of the Paris Agreement also establishes the Global Goal on Adaptation (GGA), which aims to enhance adaptive capacity, strengthen resilience, and reduce vulnerability to climate change. To operationalize the GGA, the UAE Framework for Global Climate Resilience was adopted at CMA5, containing seven thematic targets and four dimensional targets. The inclusion of MoI aspects in the relevant decision (Decision 2/CMA5) is mostly focused on finance. **On MoI generally, the CMA “[r]ecognizes that means of implementation for adaptation, such as finance, technology transfer and capacity-building, are crucial to the implementation of the United Arab Emirates Framework for Global Climate Resilience”** and “[r]eiterates that continuous and enhanced international support provided and mobilized for developing country Parties, in accordance with the provisions of Articles 9-11 of the Paris Agreement, is urgently required, taking into account the needs and priorities of developing country Parties, to support the implementation of the UAE Framework for Global Climate Resilience, including towards achieving the targets referred to in paragraphs 9–10 above.”¹

CMA5 also launched the two-year UAE-Belém work programme on indicators to adopt a GGA indicator package at CMA7. At CMA6, Parties decided that the final outcome of the UAE-Belém work programme should include, “where applicable,” and inter alia, “quantitative and qualitative indicators for enabling factors for the implementation of adaptation action, including means of implementation.”²

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Adaptation technology is mainstreamed into Mol within the UNFCCC process, as well as also provided through dedicated instruments. The Paris Agreement states that support for the implementation of Article 10 (technology development and transfer) shall be provided to developing country Parties “with a view to achieving a balance between support for mitigation and adaptation.”³

The technology framework adopted by CMA1 in 2018 elaborates on this under each of its key themes of innovation; implementation; enabling environment and capacity-building; collaboration and stakeholder engagement; and support.⁴ Additionally, the current Joint Work Programme of the Technology Mechanism between the Technology Executive Committee (TEC) and the Climate Technology Centre and Network (CTCN) commits to a number of common areas of work focused on adaptation, notably within the theme of “water-energy-food systems.”⁵ Regarding technical assistance, 31.1% of requests to the CTCN so far have had an adaptation objective, while 28.5% have been cross-cutting.⁶ Of the adaptation requests, 34.5% are related to water, followed by 15.5% concerning agriculture and forestry, and 13.8% concerning coastal zones.

The Green Climate Fund (GCF), the largest multilateral climate fund and an operating entity of the Financial Mechanism, is an example of the mainstreaming of adaptation technology.

Adaptation accounts for 48% of nominal funding from the GCF.⁷ The GCF reports that 83% of its approved projects “included technology components.” Of these projects, 16% focused on adaptation technologies and 19% on “cross-cutting” technologies.⁸ The Adaptation Fund Climate Innovation Accelerator is an example of a dedicated window for grant-based financing to support adaptation innovation, including technologies. It has been implemented by UNEP (with CTCN as executing entity) and UNDP and is now in its second phase.⁹

This technical brief aims to provide an outline of the UNFCCC’s Technology Mechanism as well as important considerations and possibilities related to the inclusion of climate technology as part of Mol in the GGA indicators.

Interlinkages between adaptation and Mol within the Paris Agreement

- *Article 7.13: “Continuous and enhanced international support shall be provided to developing country Parties for the implementation of paragraphs 7, 9, 10 and 11 of this Article, in accordance with the provisions of Articles 9, 10 and 11.”*
- *Article 7.7 and 7.9 concern adaptation cooperation and actions, while 7.10 and 7.11 refer to adaptation communications.*
- *Articles 9, 10, and 11 concern finance, technology development and transfer (TDT), and capacity-building, respectively. “Means of implementation” (MOI), as these three categories of support are collectively referred to, are therefore fundamentally linked to the adaptation actions of developing countries under the Paris Agreement.*

I. The Technology Mechanism under the UNFCCC Process

The Technology Mechanism (which comprises the TEC and CTCN) was established at COP16 (2010) to facilitate the implementation of actions to achieve “the objective of enhanced action on technology development and transfer is to support action on mitigation and adaptation in order to achieve the full implementation of the Convention.”¹⁰

The CTCN facilitates a network of diverse institutions in order to respond to developing country requests for technical assistance, engage in capacity-building and provide knowledge management services.¹¹ The Climate Technology Centre is hosted by UNEP by agreement with the COP. The CTCN has an Advisory Board with core responsibilities such as approving the CTCN budget and the appointment of its director and approving and providing guidance on various matters.¹² The CTCN has been fully operational since 2014. At the time of writing the CTCN had over 900 Network members and had engaged in over 400 technical assistance projects, either completed or in various stages of progress.¹³

The Technology Mechanism serves both the Convention (COP) and the Paris Agreement (CMA).¹⁴ **In 2018, the CMA adopted a Technology Framework that provides overarching guidance to the Technology Mechanism’s work under the Paris Agreement.** The TEC and CTCN have been working increasingly closely together in recent years. In 2022, following the experience of several joint activities, the two bodies adopted a Joint Work Programme for 2023-27.

Adaptation technologies within the TM

A vast range of technologies is used within the context of adaptation. Alongside specific technologies, Parties can make systemic interventions to strengthen the contribution of technology to adaptation. The 2025 synthesis report of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) found a “notable increase” in the share of Parties including broader technology measures such as “innovation, research and development,” “policy, regulatory and legal measures,” and “institutional strengthening and coordination.”¹⁵

Functions of the TEC and the CTCN

The TEC’s functions include to provide an overview of technological needs, recommend guidance on policies and actions, and to seek cooperation with other initiatives and stakeholders.¹⁶ Its typical mode of work is to organise events that inform the production of knowledge products, which are distilled into TEC briefs, which include key messages and recommendations to the COP, CMA, and other addressees. It also has various other mandated functions, such as providing inputs to the Standing Committee on Finance’s draft guidance to the operating entities of the Financial Mechanism. Underlining the expert nature of the TEC’s work, members are to serve “in their personal capacity.”¹⁷

The CTCN functions as the operational body, or implementation arm, of the Technology Mechanism, delivering technical aid and capacity-building assistance to developing nations. The CTCN plays a critical role in promoting the rapid uptake of technology for low-carbon and climate-resilient development at the request of developing countries. By facilitating technology transfer and deployment through matchmaking, advisory services, and knowledge sharing, and by providing a wide range of technical assistance to developing countries, the CTCN aims to overcome technology barriers and promote sustainable development. It is supported through voluntary contributions from donor countries and other sources, and works closely with financial entities to maximise the mobilisation of resources for climate action.

Commonly mentioned technologies measures related to agrifood systems, climate monitoring and observations, and the water sector, as well as cross-cutting or multi-sector measures such as digital solutions including AI.¹⁸

In 2021, the then UNEP-DTU and the Green Technology Center Korea produced a **“taxonomy” of climate change adaptation technologies, to be used as a guidebook for adaptation technology needs assessments (TNAs)**.¹⁹ TNAs are a process under the UNFCCC through which developing countries identify, prioritize, and plan for the technologies they need for climate action, including analysis of barriers for acquiring them and how to overcome them.²⁰ The taxonomy groups adaptation technologies into six categories: agriculture and livestock; water; forestry and land; marine, fisheries, and coastal zones; health; and climate change forecast and monitoring.

Within each category, there are several technology sections (42 in total). For example, within climate forecast and monitoring, one category is climate risk analysis, prediction, and assessment, defined as including “the establishment of information production systems aimed at producing customized information on climate change and services that enable users to easily access information or data on climate change.” Examples of specific technologies follow, such as technology for producing and storing climate data.²¹

Recent TEC publications with relevance to adaptation in developing countries

- *The technical paper on AI for climate action, which discusses AI applications in several areas of adaptation, including early warning systems, earth observation, and disaster risk reduction.*²²
- *The policy brief (produced jointly with GEO) on innovation and technology in support of the UN Secretary-General’s Early Warnings for All (EW4All) initiative.*²³
- *The joint publication with FAO on climate technologies for agrifood systems transformation, including country-specific adaptation examples.*²⁴
- *The 2023 Climate Technology Progress Report (produced jointly with the UNEP Copenhagen Climate Centre and the CTCN), which discusses technologies for both adaptation and mitigation in urban contexts.*²⁵
- *A set of knowledge products on collaborative research, development, and demonstration.*²⁶
- *Joint policy briefs on technologies for addressing loss and damage (L&D) in coastal zones as well as innovative approaches for strengthening ocean/coastal adaptation.*²⁷
- *The paper on innovative approaches to accelerating and scaling up technology implementation for mitigation or adaptation.*²⁸

At the level of specific technologies, the most recent (2020) TNA synthesis report identified the most prioritised technologies. As outlined there, the most prioritised sectors include agriculture, forestry and land use, and water. For agriculture, the top three technologies were sprinkler and drip irrigation; crop diversification and new varieties; and drought-resistant crop varieties.

Adaptation technologies and the GGA

Adaptation technologies have a clear role to play in achieving the GGA targets adopted by CMA5 in 2023. The seven thematic targets for “2030 and progressively beyond,” such as “significantly reducing climate-induced water scarcity and enhancing climate resilience to water-related hazards towards a climate-resilient water supply, climate-resilient sanitation, and access to safe and affordable potable water for all”³¹ (target 9a), correspond closely to the technology categories discussed above.

Regarding the dimensional targets, cross-cutting technologies (such as information sensors) are particularly salient to the dimensional target 10a (impact, vulnerability, and risk assessment), while all technologies, as well as systemic technology measures, have a role to play for the dimensional target 10c (implementation).³²

For water, rainwater harvesting was most prioritized, followed by sub-surface water storage and use, and small reservoirs, small dams etc.²⁹ Similar findings on priority technologies were reported in the GST synthesis report on Mol.³⁰

Technology would be a necessary input for making progress measurable for most of the potential indicators proposed by the experts convened by the SB Chairs after SB60 in 2024, which have produced a preliminary list of 100 indicator options. This is clearly the case even for the majority of potential indicators that do not mention technology explicitly, as information technologies will be necessary for measuring performance against the goals and indicators.

II. Overview of the GGA negotiations

The UAE Framework for Global Climate Resilience aims to guide the achievement of the GGA and the review of overall progress in achieving it. It promotes inclusive, science-based adaptation efforts that enhance resilience, reduce vulnerabilities, and protect livelihoods, nature, and well-being now and for future generations in line with the temperature goal of the Paris Agreement while respecting Indigenous Peoples' local, and traditional knowledge and values.

As outlined above, [Decision 2/CMA.5](#) established seven thematic and four dimensional targets and launched the 2024-2025 UAE-Belém work programme on indicators. The Subsidiary Bodies were requested to initiate the process of undertaking the UAE-Belém work programme at [SB60](#) (June 2024), after which the SB Chairs convened technical experts to initiate the work on indicators.

At [CMA6](#), it was decided that **the final outcome of the UAE-Belém work programme may include a manageable set of no more than 100 indicators** that (a) are globally applicable with a view to informing an analysis of relevant global trends; (b) constitute a menu that captures various contexts of adaptation action; and (c) are designed to enable assessment of progress towards achieving the different components of the targets.

At SB62, based on the progress made by the convened experts, Parties concluded that additional time and guidance were needed to develop GGA indicators. In that regard, further guidance was provided to the experts towards the conclusion of their work in August 2025 in accordance with [paragraph 15 of the draft conclusions proposed by the SB Chairs \(FCCC/SB/2025/L.4\)](#).

This additional guidance aims to ensure that the final list of indicators are manageable and in accordance with the mandate from decision 3/CMA.6. **Ahead of CMA7, the experts have submitted their final list of 100 indicator options across all targets.**

Technology aspects in the GGA indicators developed by experts post-SB62

Technology transfer and development, along with finance and capacity-building, is a key component of the means to implement climate action, both adaptation and mitigation. **Access to technology development and transfer is crucial for tracking the operationalization of GGA targets, but explicit mentions in the list of indicator options are limited.** Technology is mentioned in the indicator list at two different levels: through direct reference at the indicator level, and through references in the rationale or additional context for proposed indicators (see table below).

Table 1: Overview of relevant indicators

Explicit reference in indicator name	Reference in rationale or additional context	
10c09	9a02, 9b02	Rationale for indicator
	9g03	Description of the indicator
	10a10	Data availability
	9b01, 9b02, 10c06, 10c08	Disaggregated levels

Target 10c (implementation) makes explicit reference to technology within the title of indicator 10c09. This indicator would enable developing countries in tracking the technological needs and in implementing National Adaptation Plans (NAPs), policies, and strategies, with two options outlined:

Table 2: Indicators with explicit reference in indicator name

Indicator reference	Indicator name
10c09	[Option 1] Level of implementation of adaptation technology needs identified by developing countries, including needs expressed in TNAs, NAPs, NDCs, and other equivalent policy instruments, including their development and transfer from developed to developing countries.
	[Option 2] Level of implementation of adaptation technology needs identified by Parties, including needs expressed in TNAs, NAPs, NDCs, and other equivalent policy instruments including their development and transfer

The overall aim of this indicator is to measure the implementation of adaptation technology, with the options diverging on the direction of technology development and transfer. Option 1 clearly indicates the direction from developed to developing countries while option 2 is general and does not refer to the direction of support.

Additionally, through this indicator, the collaboration is not solely limited to direction of support, but also collaboration with other actors such as practitioners and users of technology.

Furthermore, under option 2, the indicator also aims to capture technology collaboration between developing countries in addition to the developed to developing collaboration or transfer. As explained by the experts in their technical report, due to its political nature this matter could not be resolved at the technical level and was therefore forwarded as options for resolution at the political level.³³

This indicator also identifies interlinkages to other targets such as 9a (water supply and sanitation), 9b (food and agricultural production), 9c (health impacts and health services), 9d (ecosystems and biodiversity), 9e (infrastructure and human settlements), 9f (poverty eradication and livelihoods), 9g (cultural heritage and knowledge), 10a (impact, vulnerability, and risk assessment), 10d (monitoring, evaluation, and learning). The experts also agreed that the data needed for measuring this indicator would be available within and beyond the UNFCCC process.

The indicator that references technological aspects within its rationale highlights the pivotal role of technology in advancing adaptation actions under the thematic targets.

For instance, indicators that measure progress in water efficiency rely on innovative technologies to enhance water use in sectors such as agriculture. Moreover, the implementation of measures related to impacts, vulnerability, and risk assessments depends on advanced technologies for collecting data and forecasting climate risks, thereby supporting countries in designing effective national climate actions.

Advanced and innovative technologies are therefore embedded within several indicators, including 9a02, 9b02, 9g03, 10a10, 9b01, 9b02, 10c06, and 10c08.

III. Connecting adaptation technology with the GGA

Article 7.9 of the Paris Agreement focuses on adaptation planning processes and the implementation of actions by Parties, which entails specific adaptation actions across different sectors, such as the ones outlined by the seven thematic targets of the GGA. It also outlines the importance of assessing climate change impacts and vulnerabilities, “with a view to formulating nationally determined prioritized actions, taking into account vulnerable people, places and ecosystems.”

As part of this process Parties could also identify technology needs and channel work on technology development and transfer. This is especially the case given the interconnections and synergies between different sectors and targets and the categories of climate adaptation technology discussed above.

The potential indicators and their additional information are even more targeted and sometimes imply appropriate technologies. The eventual indicators could therefore be used, for example, to inform project proposals to multilateral development banks (MDBs), climate funds, or the CTCN.

Many factors can contribute to an enabling environment for technology development and transfer. **Based on a mapping of TNAs, NDCs, and technical assistance provided by the CTCN, the TEC identified the following categories of enabling factors (in declining order of frequency):**

- Economic and financial
- Information and awareness
- Legal and regulatory
- Technical
- Institutional and organizational
- Human skills
- Network
- Market conditions
- Social, cultural, and behavioural.³⁴

The TEC found that governments play a key role in shaping an enabling environment and addressing related challenges, including through macroeconomic policy, policies to incentivise technology adoption, legal and regulatory frameworks, establishing technology standards, market interventions and education and training.³⁵

The TEC, as noted above, has undertaken collaborative work focused on adaptation technologies with a number of other bodies. **Some key takeaways of this work can be summarised as follows:**

Realising EW4All:

The TEC recommends that the COP and the CMA encourage Parties, international organisations and stakeholders, as relevant, to consider technologies for multi-hazard early warning systems (MHEWS) when preparing and updating NDCs, NAPs, TNAs, and other national strategies and plans; invest in multisectoral technology solutions by leveraging funding from relevant financial mechanisms and other sources; leverage international initiatives and public-private partnerships in order to strengthen the capacity of governments to understand and mitigate context-specific disaster risks; support the integration of technologies into projects to promote local stakeholder engagement; build the technical capacity of stakeholders in developing countries for enhancing reporting on, production, use of and access to risk knowledge; and leverage the global community of scientific experts and innovators.

Innovative approaches for strengthening coastal and ocean adaptation:

Recommendations for policymakers including national and local governments, are to embed integrated solutions into climate-related policies as well as other sectors; translate national policies into localized adaptation action; strengthen governance and technical capacities of relevant national and local management institutions; prioritize the most vulnerable communities, societal groups, and ecosystems.

Technologies for averting, minimizing and addressing L&D in coastal zones:

For technologies for risk assessment, there are a number of areas where further improvements can be made: increased awareness of existing technologies; availability and accessibility of high-quality and timely data; appropriate methods and tools for considering multiple hazard types (rapid and slow onset events); and appropriate scales of governance. Technologies for risk retention provide measures for the protection, retention and long-term adaptability of coastal zones and may take the form of structural/engineered measures, organizational and financial planning, legal and regulatory measures, ecosystem-based approaches to adaptation, community-based adaptation, and contingency planning and innovation. These measures require an integrated cross-sectoral approach to coastal zone management. Improving technologies for coastal risk retention is a continuous process and should be supported through the systematic sharing of knowledge and practices. The complex nature of efforts to avert, minimize and address L&D in coastal zones requires different technologies for recovery and rehabilitation, since recovery and rehabilitation happen over multiple time scales, and priorities may shift as a situation progresses.

IV. Conclusions

Technology development and transfer are critical means of implementation for climate action, including adaptation. In response to this fact, the UNFCCC process has established the Technology Mechanism to guide the implementation of technology development and transfer, with two permanent bodies that formulate policy aspects (the TEC) and implementation (the CTCN).

As the Global Goal on Adaptation is currently being operationalized, it is important to integrate technology for the planning and implementation of adaptation action as part of Mol. **The current list of 100 indicator options developed under the UAE-Belém work programme make reference to important aspects of technology fundamentally at two levels:** directly, with an explicit reference at the indicator level (indicator 10c09), and through references in the rationale or additional context for proposed indicators (indicators 9a02, 9b02, 9g03, 10a10, 9b01, 9b02, 10c06, and 10c08).

The indicator options and their additional information are more explicitly targeted and in some cases imply appropriate technologies. If these indicators are adopted, this information could be used, for example, to inform project proposals to MDBs, climate funds, or the CTCN, in addition to tracking progress towards the targets of the GGA.

Understanding the role of technology is crucial for a robust decision at COP30 that connects technology development and transfer as part of Mol with the relevant existing processes under or involving the Technology Mechanism and the work of the TEC and CTCN.

Organizational profile

SLYCAN Trust is a non-profit think tank working on climate change, sustainable development, climate finance, risk management, entrepreneurship, biodiversity and ecosystem conservation, security, and social justice including gender and youth empowerment. Our work spans the national, regional, and global level from policy analysis and evidence-based research to capacity-building, technical support provision, and on-the-ground implementation.

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